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Reducing the infectivity and richness of ectomycorrhizal fungi in a calcareous *Quercus ilex* forest through soil preparations for truffle plantation establishment: a bioassay study

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Abstract

In the early years of a black truffle plantation, the field proliferation of the nursery-inoculated fungi can be hampered by native ectomycorrhizal fungi colonising the seedling roots. Reducing the soil ectomycorrhizal infectivity in the planting hole before introducing the inoculated seedling could be an effective strategy to reduce this problem. Three bioassays were conducted to evaluate the impact of several soil preparations on the ectomycorrhizal infectivity and richness of a *Quercus ilex* soil in a truffle-producing region. Microwaves, quicklime and acetic acid significantly decreased the percent root colonisation and morphotype richness of the native ectomycorrhizal fungi. However, they also decreased seedling survival or growth. Peracetic acid, hydrogen peroxide and sodium hypochlorite did not show a significant negative effect on the soil ectomycorrhizal community. The results support the potential of soil preparation for reducing the ectomycorrhizal infectivity of forest soils, thus being a promising strategy to reduce the early colonisation by native fungi in truffle plantations. However, the indications of damage to the seedling development must be addressed.

Keywords: ectomycorrhizal infectivity, microwaves, liming, acetic acid

1 Introduction

Ectomycorrhizal (EM) fungi are used to improve the establishment, health and growth of forest plantations (Marx et al. 2002) and are also cultivated as economic crops (Hall and Zambonelli 2012). The cultivation of the black truffle (*Tuber melanosporum* Vitt.) is one of the most advanced, although not completely domesticated yet (Reyna and Garcia-Barreda 2014).

For these purposes the seedlings are usually inoculated in the nursery. However, in the field the persistence of the nursery-inoculated fungi can be hampered by native (soil borne) EM fungi colonising the seedling roots and limiting the number of root tips available for the introduced fungus (Jones et al. 2003; Sourzat et al. 2010; De Miguel et al. 2014). Competitive EM species adapted to the local environment can displace the introduced fungus from the roots (Águeda et al. 2010), especially during the early years in the field when the introduced fungus is more vulnerable (De Miguel et al. 2014). This is especially the case in soils previously occupied by EM plants, such as *Quercus* or *Pinus*, or surrounded by a matrix of mature EM vegetation (Reyna et al. 2006; Sourzat et al. 2010).

In these soils, reducing the EM infectivity in the planting hole before introducing the nursery seedling could be an effective strategy to reduce the early colonisation by native fungi, increase the receptiveness to the introduced fungus and improve the performance of inoculated plantations. However, few soil preparations have been evaluated for this purpose. Soil heating has a proved effect on EM populations (Neary et al. 1999), but the use of prescribed burning in the Mediterranean basin is controversial. The impact of soil liming on EM populations is well established for acid soils (Taylor and Finlay 2003), although not for alkaline soils. Garcia-Barreda and Reyna (2013) found that soil heating reduced the richness of native EM in *T. melanosporum* inoculated seedlings, whereas no significant effect of liming was found at the dose applied. Acetic acid (AA), sodium hypochlorite (SH) and

hydrogen peroxide (HP) are broadly used as disinfectants in the agri-food industry and sanitation (Block 2001) and have been tested against soil-borne pathogenic fungi (Doran 1932; Gerritse et al. 1992; Angelova et al. 2005), but their effects on EM fungi have been scarcely studied.

We aim to assess the effectiveness of several soil preparations, alternative to soil burning, for reducing the EM infectivity of forest soils. As a secondary aim we assess the impact of these soil preparations on *Quercus ilex* L. seedling growth during their first year of life, particularly on fine roots, on which EM fungi depend. Bioassays were used to test two microwaves treatments, five doses of quicklime (calcium oxide), AA, and two doses of peracetic acid, SH and HP.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study site and experimental design

The study was conducted in the black truffle producing region of El Toro (eastern Spain, 40°0' N, 0°46' W, 1050 m a.s.l.). The soil is a calcixercept developed on hard limestone (clay loam texture, pH 8.0, organic matter 6.8%, stoniness 40% vol./vol., bulk density: 1.03 kg l⁻¹). It is covered by a mature EM forest of *Quercus ilex* – *Quercus faginea* 900-1700 trees ha⁻¹.

Three bioassays were conducted to assess the EM infectivity in the treated soils. We used dense forest soils in the bioassays instead of open forests because the former present higher EM richness (Yamashita et al. 2007), thus allowing to show the effect of soil preparations on more EM species.

2.1.1 Quicklime treatments

Four different quicklime doses (0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 kg m⁻²) and two control treatments (absolute and procedural) were compared. In October 2004 the forest soil was dug (0.2 m depth) and

the four quicklime treatments were applied using quicklime powder (94% calcium oxide, particle diameter < 0.1 m, Cales Pascual). Part of the dug soil was not limed (procedural control, 0 kg m⁻²). In March 2005 the soil was collected. Undisturbed soil (not previously dug) was used as absolute control. The pH of the soil was monitored from October 2004 to March 2005 (rainfall: 140 mm): in the control the pH remained between 8.1-8.4, in the 0.5 kg m⁻² treatment it raised to 8.8 for the first three months, in the 1-1.5 kg m⁻² treatments it raised to 11.9 for the first two months and in the 2 kg m⁻² treatment it raised above 12 for the first four months. In March 2005, all treatments showed pH ranging 8.1-8.4.

2.1.2 Microwaves, sodium hypochlorite and acetic acid treatments

Five soil treatments (microwaves 90 s, microwaves 180 s, SH 70 g m⁻², SH 280 g m⁻², AA 315 g m⁻²) and a procedural control were tested, in a full factorial design with another variable: cultivation time of the bioassay (7 and 13 months).

In November 2006 the soil was dug (0.15 m depth) and homogenised by mixing. The SH and AA treatments were applied, dissolved in water to obtain a uniform distribution. In May 2007 the soil was collected and the microwaves treatments were applied, with a domestic microwave oven, nominal maximum power 700 W at a frequency 2.45 GHz. The soil was put in a layer 2.5 cm depth to obtain a homogeneous temperature. In the 90 s treatment the soil reached 65°C at 1.2 cm depth, and in the 180 s treatment it reached 86°C. In May 2007 the pH was similar in all the treatments and the control (8.3-8.4).

2.1.3 Hydrogen peroxide, Proxitane and quicklime treatments

Five soil treatments (HP 0.6 kg m⁻², HP 2.1 kg m⁻², Proxitane ® 5:23 2.2 kg m⁻², Proxitane ® 5:23 7.7 kg m⁻², quicklime 4 kg m⁻²) and a procedural control were tested, in a full factorial

design with two more variables: land use (forest soil and *Q. ilex* hedgerow in a cereal culture) and cultivation time of the bioassay (6, 8 and 11 months).

In February 2009 the soil was dug (0.25 m depth), homogenised by mixing and the treatments were applied. The HP and Proxitane were applied dissolved in water to obtain a uniform distribution. Proxitane ® 5:23 (Solvay) contains 5% peracetic acid, 20% HP and 10% AA (w/w). In April 2009 the soil was collected. At that moment the pH was similar in all the treatments (8.3-8.5, rainfall February-April: 100 mm), except for the quicklime and the Proxitane treatments in the *Quercus* hedgerow soil (9.4 and 8.9, respectively).

2.2 Seedling cultivation and data collection

Within five days after collecting the soil of a bioassay, it was mixed with perlite (10:1) and used to fill Quick-pot® 0.65 l containers (18 cm depth). A *Q. ilex* seedling was planted in each container (n=54 for the quicklime assay; n=72 for the microwaves-SH-AA assay; n=72 for the HP-Proxitane assay). The seedlings had been germinated in sterile substrate (perlite, vermiculite) in January and were transplanted when they presented abundant fine roots (March-May) to minimise the time that the soil was free of root tips available for EM infection (*Quercus* do not produce root tips until several weeks after germination, Harmer 1990). *Quercus ilex* was chosen because it is the most used host tree in Spanish truffle plantations.

The containers were watered to saturation every 2-3 days and were kept outdoors to avoid glasshouse-adapted EM fungi. The seedlings were sampled after one vegetative period, the quicklime assay being conducted from March 2005 to March 2006, the microwaves-SH-AA assay from May 2007 to June 2008 (with an additional sampling in December 2007), and the HP-Proxitane assay from April 2009 to April 2010 (with additional samplings in October and December 2009).

In the quicklime bioassay the percent root colonisation was assessed through random sampling. The fine roots (diameter < 2 mm) were cut under water in portions with length < 1 cm and spread over a grid 3 × 3 cm. Half the grid squares were randomly selected and the root tips were counted. The tips were classified as non-mycorrhizal or mycorrhizal, and the latter were sorted in morphotypes (Agerer 1987-2002; De Román 2003, Table S1). The seedlings were dried to constant weight at 80°C.

In the remaining bioassays, the seedling root colonisation was assessed through volumetric sampling, following the methodology described in Garcia-Barreda and Reyna (2013). In each pot, a composite sample (9% of the substrate volume, 58 ml) was produced with three horizontal cores 2 cm diameter (the pot depth was divided into three equal parts and a core was taken in the centre of each one).

2.3 Statistical analysis

The effect of soil preparation on percent root colonisation, number of native EM morphotypes per sample, seedling dry weight and fine root (diameter < 2 mm) dry weight was assessed through ANOVAs. A least significant difference test with Bonferroni correction was used to identify significant differences among treatments. When the model assumptions were violated, the response variable was transformed. The number of root tips per seedling was included as a covariate in the ANOVA of the EM morphotype richness to account for the differences in morphotype richness caused by the degree of fine root development. The frequency of appearance of the EM morphotypes (proportion of samples in which they were present) was analysed through logistic regression when it was not possible to analyse their specific percent root colonisation.

3 Results

3.1 Quicklime

No significant differences in the percent root colonisation were found between the procedural control (0 kg m⁻²) and the remaining treatments, although it was slightly higher in the absolute control (Table 1). Morphotype richness was significantly higher in the absolute than in the procedural control, with no significant differences between the latter and the quicklime treatments (Table 1). Morphotype richness was not significantly related to the number of root tips (P = 0.10).

Eleven EM morphotypes were found in the bioassay. *Cenococcum geophilum* Fr. and the complex *Tuber albidum* Pico were the most frequent and abundant ones, but no significant association between the quicklime dose and their occurrence was found (Tables S2, S3).

No significant differences were found between the seedling dry weight in the procedural control and the remaining treatments (Table 1). The fine root dry weight was significantly lower in the 1 kg m⁻² treatment than in both controls (Table 1). In the remaining quicklime treatments it was also lower than in the controls, but not significantly.

Table 1 – Mean characteristics (and standard error) of the seedlings planted in soils treated with quicklime. Letters indicate significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) among treatments.

	Root colonisation (%)	No morphotypes per sample	Seedling dry weight (g)	Dry weight of fine roots (g) ^a
Absolute control	36.3 (3.1)a	4.3 (0.3)a	2.56 (0.17)ab	1.20 (0.28) a
0 kg m ⁻²	30.6 (2.5)ab	3.1 (0.1)b	2.50 (0.20)ab	1.02 (0.37) a
0.5kg m ⁻²	32.7 (4.1)ab	2.8 (0.3)b	2.03 (0.22)b	0.35 (0.15) ab
1 kg m ⁻²	29.8 (3.8)ab	3.1 (0.3)b	2.04 (0.23)b	0.22 (0.10) b
1.5 kg m ⁻²	19.7 (3.2)b	2.7 (0.3)b	2.99 (0.17)a	0.77 (0.30) ab
2 kg m ⁻²	27.7 (2.5)ab	3.2 (0.3)ab	2.35 (0.12)ab	0.58 (0.10) ab

^a Variable log transformed (standard error derived from the upper limit of the transformed variable)

3.2 Microwaves, sodium hypochlorite and acetic acid

The microwaves 180 s and the AA treatments showed significantly lower percent root colonisation than the control (Table 2). Morphotype richness was positively related to the number of root tips in the seedling ($P = 0.04$); after removing the effect of this variable, only both microwaves treatments showed lower morphotype richness than the control (Table 2). Neither the percent root colonisation ($P = 0.78$) nor the morphotype richness ($P = 0.91$) were significantly related to the cultivation time.

Thirteen EM morphotypes were found in the bioassay (Table S4). Four of them (*Tuber aestivum* Vitt., complex *T. albidum*, Unidentified 6 and *C. geophilum*) were present in almost all the samples of the control treatment, with the former two being dominant. The percent root colonisation of the complex *T. albidum* was significantly lower in the SH 70 g m⁻² treatment than in the control (Table S5). The root colonisation of *T. aestivum* and *C. geophilum* and the appearance frequency of type Thelephoroid and complex *T. albidum* were significantly lower in the microwaves 180s treatment than in the control, whereas the root colonisation of type Unidentified 6 was significantly higher in the microwaves 90 s treatment than in the control. The root colonisation of *T. aestivum* was significantly lower in the AA treatment than in the control. The appearance frequency of type *Pisolithus* increased in the microwaves 180 s and both SH treatments, although the differences with the control were not statistically significant (Tables S4, S5).

The microwaves 180 s treatment was the only one with a significant and negative effect on the seedling dry weight (Table 2). Although the AA treatment did not significantly affect seedling weight, 42% of these seedlings died before the 7 months of cultivation (in the remaining treatments, only one seedling out of 60 died). The fine root dry weight was positively related to the cultivation time ($P < 0.001$), but no soil preparation showed significant differences from the control (Table 2).

Table 2 – Mean characteristics (and standard error) of the seedlings planted in soils treated with microwaves, SH and AA. Letters indicate significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) among treatments.

	Root colonisation (%)	No morphotypes per sample	Seedling dry weight (g) ^a	Dry weight of fine roots (g) ^a
Soil preparation				
Control	45.6 (2.3)a	4.8 (0.3)a	3.58 (0.36)a	0.91 (0.12)ab
Microwaves 90 s	38.5 (2.1)ab	3.3 (0.3)b	3.52 (0.43)a	0.87 (0.13)ab
Microwaves 180 s	25.6 (4.1)c	1.8 (0.3)c	2.71 (0.35)b	0.68 (0.10)b
SH 70 g m ⁻²	39.3 (2.3)ab	4.6 (0.3)a	3.00 (0.36)ab	0.81 (0.14)ab
SH 280 g m ⁻²	43.1 (2.9)ab	4.5 (0.4)ab	3.32 (0.48)ab	0.96 (0.14)a
AA 315 g m ⁻²	31.6 (2.7)bc	4.3 (0.4)ab	3.17 (0.50)a	0.74 (0.13)ab
Cultivation time				
7 months	37.1 (2.1)	3.7 (0.3)	2.35 (0.10)j	0.57 (0.03)j
13 months	38.2 (1.9)	4.0 (0.3)	4.54 (0.16)i	1.24 (0.07)i

^a Variables log transformed (standard error derived from the upper limit of the transformed variable)

3.3 Hydrogen peroxide, Proxitan and quicklime

The percent root colonisation was significantly lower in the quicklime treatment than in the control (Table 3). Morphotype richness was positively related to the number of root tips in the seedling ($P = 0.03$); after removing the effect of this variable, morphotype richness was significantly lower in the quicklime treatment than in the control and significantly higher in the HP 0.6 kg m⁻² treatment than in the control (Table 3). Both the percent root colonisation and the morphotype richness were positively related to the forest soil ($P = 0.02$ and 0.001 , respectively) and the cultivation time ($P < 0.001$ and $P = 0.009$, respectively).

Fourteen EM morphotypes were found in the bioassay, although seven appeared only in 1-3 samples (Table S6). The appearance frequency of three of the four most common morphotypes was significantly associated with one land use. The root colonisation of complex *T. albidum* and the appearance frequency of type *Genea* were significantly lower in the quicklime treatment than in the control, and none of the rarer morphotypes appeared in the limed soil (Tables S6, S7). The HP treatments were not significantly related to the occurrence

of any morphotype, but the seven rarer morphotypes were present in some of the HP treatments. The Proxitane treatments were not significantly related to any morphotype occurrence but type *Genea*. None of the rarer morphotypes appeared in the Proxitane treatments (Tables S6, S7).

The seedling dry weight was positively related to the forest soil ($P < 0.01$), but no significant effect of the soil preparation ($P = 0.58$) or the cultivation time ($P = 0.35$) was found (Table 3). However, in the *Quercus* hedgerow soil treated with quicklime 67% of the seedlings died before the 6 months of cultivation, whereas in the remaining combinations of land use and soil preparation only four seedling out of 66 died. The fine root dry weight was positively related to the forest soil ($P = 0.001$), but no significant effect of soil preparation ($P = 0.28$) or cultivation time ($P = 0.18$) was found (Table 3).

Table 3 – Mean characteristics (and standard error) of the seedlings planted in soils treated with HP, Proxitane and quicklime. Letters indicate significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) among treatments.

	Root colonisation (%) ^a	No morphotypes per sample	Seedling dry weight (g)	Dry weight of fine roots (g)
Soil preparation				
Control	20.2 (7.0)a	2.0 (0.3)b	1.85 (0.18)	0.43 (0.06)
HP 0.6 kg m ⁻²	26.8 (4.7)a	3.5 (0.5)a	1.72 (0.16)	0.40 (0.06)
HP 2.1 kg m ⁻²	24.3 (6.6)a	2.3 (0.4)ab	1.95 (0.24)	0.52 (0.09)
Proxitane 2.2 kg m ⁻²	18.6 (11.4)a	1.5 (0.4)bc	1.66 (0.21)	0.41 (0.06)
Proxitane 7.7 kg m ⁻²	19.3 (8.4)a	1.9 (0.3)bc	1.65 (0.18)	0.37 (0.06)
Quicklime 4 kg m ⁻²	2.6 (2.7)b	0.6 (0.2)c	1.71 (0.28)	0.39 (0.12)
Land use				
Forest	23.6 (4.0)p	2.4 (0.2)p	2.11 (0.10) p	0.55 (0.04)p
<i>Q. ilex</i> hedgerow in cereal culture	12.1 (4.1)q	1.6 (0.2)q	1.35 (0.09) q	0.27 (0.03)q
Cultivation time				
6 months	7.7 (3.1)k	1.6 (0.3)j	1.61 (0.14)	0.39 (0.05)
8 months	19.5 (4.1)j	1.9 (0.2)j	1.79 (0.11)	0.47 (0.05)
11 months	42.0 (3.7)i	2.8 (0.4)i	1.94 (0.18)	0.40 (0.05)

^a Variable log transformed (standard error derived from the upper limit of the transformed variable)

4 Discussion

The success of the cultivation of EM fungi depends on the ability of their mycorrhizas to persist and proliferate in the field. The infectivity of native EM populations plays an important role in the receptiveness of a soil to the introduced EM association (Pera and Parladé 2005). Reducing the EM infectivity in the soil where the seedling is being outplanted would reduce early invasion from native fungi, which is a major problem in truffle cultivation (Sourzat et al. 2010; De Miguel et al. 2014).

In our soil, the microwaves treatment reaching 86°C reduced the infectivity and the morphotype richness to half. The microwaves treatment reaching 65°C significantly reduced the morphotype richness but not the soil EM infectivity, similarly to that found by Garcia-Barreda and Reyna (2013) in truffle-inoculated seedlings. Neary et al. (1999) considered that biological disruption of fungal mycelia in soils occurs in the 60-80°C range, but Izzo et al. (2006) pointed the relevance of resistant propagules in maintaining the EM infectivity of heated soils.

The response to heating in our EM community is species-specific. Peay et al. (2009) found that the sensitivity of EM propagules to heating varied among species. Besides decreasing the abundance of effective propagules, soil heating can also affect post-treatment fungal growth (Gibson et al. 1988; Bárcenas-Moreno and Baath 2010). In our study, types *Pisolithus* and Unidentified 6 increased their occurrence in some of the microwaves treatments. This could be due to soil heating stimulating the germination of these species or to these species taking advantage of the gap left by the disturbance (Izzo et al. 2006). *Pisolithus* species are regarded as early colonisers and poor competitors (Cairney and Chambers 1997).

The microwaves treatment reaching 86°C also caused a 25% decrease in seedling biomass. This disagrees with the positive effect reported by Gibson et al. (1988) on *Betula pendula*

Roth.; they attributed contradictory effects on seedling biomass to the differences in soil characteristics.

In our soil, the only liming treatment that effectively reduced the EM infectivity and morphotype richness was the 4 kg m⁻², whereas in the lower ones no clear trends were found, the latter agreeing with the results of Garcia-Barreda and Reyna (2013) for inoculated seedlings in 1 kg m⁻² limed soils. Bradshaw (2005) inoculated hazel seedlings with *Hebeloma sp.* and *Scleroderma sp.* (typical native EM fungi in truffle plantations) spores and found that EM formation was negatively affected by liming with 10-40 g calcium carbonate kg⁻¹ soil (in our study the doses were 4, 8, 12, and 16 g calcium oxide kg⁻¹ fine soil in the quicklime assay, and 32 g calcium oxide kg⁻¹ fine soil in the HP-Proxitane-quicklime assay).

The occurrence of the EM morphotypes did not show any clear pattern in the 0.5-2 kg m⁻² treatments, whereas in the higher dose the occurrence of all the morphotypes seemed to decrease to a greater or lesser degree. Rineau et al. (2010) proposed that in acid soils liming modifies the ECM community composition mainly through the decrease in acidophilic fungi.

The seedlings limed with 0.5-2 kg m⁻² appeared to decrease their biomass allocation to fine roots. Helmisaari and Hallbäcken (1999) found that repeated liming increased fine root necromass and decreased fine root biomass in *Picea abies* Karsten forests, whereas Kreutzer (1995) found a positive effect on fine root production in acid soils. The decrease in fine root production could be problematic in inoculated plantations if it limited the proliferation of the introduced fungus, although in a 1 kg m⁻² liming no detrimental effect was found by Garcia-Barreda and Reyna (2013). It would be interesting to assess the use of quicklime to reduce the colonisation of the planting hole by the roots of other EM plants, since hyphae extending from living mycorrhizas are a major source of inoculum in forest soils (Jones et al. 2003).

On the other hand, the 4 kg m⁻² liming provoked a severe seedling mortality in the soil where the pH at the time of planting remained higher than before liming. This was the only liming

treatment where the pH had not returned to its pre-liming value. In acid soils the effect of liming has been attributed to proton buffering and to increase of the oxidation potential (Kreutzer 1995).

Our results point that AA can be useful to reduce soil EM infectivity, although the dose applied did not decrease morphotype richness. Doran (1932) showed that AA prevented the damages caused by damping-off fungi. The effects of AA on the microflora are mainly attributed to soil acidification and its ability to diffuse through cytoplasmic membranes (Baronofsky et al. 1984). Its effect on EM fungi has been scarcely studied: only Leake and Read (1991) reported a negative effect of 0.5 g AA kg⁻¹ dry heathland soil on *Suillus bovinus* Kuntze (in our study the dose was 3.4 g kg⁻¹ fine soil).

The bioassay raises concerns about the damage of AA on seedling development, due to the high seedling mortality. AA has been found to negatively affect growth of agricultural plants (Rao and Mikkelsen 1977). On the other hand Doran (1932) improved the germination and seedling growth of *Pinus resinosa* Sol. with AA 0.8%.

Although HP is a strong oxidiser, our treatments apparently increased soil EM infectivity and morphotype richness. HP is generated in normal fungal metabolism, but it can provoke an oxidative stress on fungal cells when its level is higher than the antioxidant defences (Angelova et al. 2005). We do not know any study assessing the effect of HP on EM fungi in the field, but Angelova et al. (2005) found HP able to decrease fungal germination and mycelial growth in 12 fungal species. The response we found to HP treatments suggests that the doses in our study were not able to trigger such an oxidative stress.

The Proxitane treatments, containing the oxidising agent peracetic acid together with AA and HP, were not effective in decreasing soil EM infectivity either.

Similarly, SH treatments did not show any significant effect on soil EM infectivity or morphotype richness despite being a strong oxidiser. We do not know any study assessing the

effect of SH on EM fungi in the field, but Gerritse et al. (1992) found it effective against the pathogenic fungus *Phytophthora cinnamomi* Rands. when added to the soil at a dose 0.5 g SH per g organic carbon (in our study the doses were 0.02 and 0.08 g per g organic carbon).

Bioassays only partly reflect the complexity of field conditions and thus their results must be interpreted with caution. They cannot take into account the EM hyphae attached to living trees as inoculum sources (Jones et al. 2003). However, our study tried to mimic the conditions in a planting hole, where a mechanical soil preparation (hole digging) is carried out before planting and the contact of the seedling with other living roots is delayed. Potted seedlings show higher fine root length than seedlings planted in the field (Tsakalidimi et al. 2009) and the watering of the bioassays was much heavier than the rainfall in the study site. However, with potted seedlings and abundant watering fine root abundance is less likely affected by environmental factors. In field experiments, the varying environmental conditions can affect seedling root growth and thus EM colonisation of roots independently of soil infectivity (Jones et al. 2003).

Despite the limitations, the bioassays proved useful as a first approach to evaluate the potential of soil preparations for our aim. The microwaves 180 s, liming 4 kg m⁻² and AA treatments reduced the EM infectivity of forest soils, although indications of damage to the seedling development were found. The bioassays detected the EM fungi in a position to colonise the fine roots of *Q. ilex* × *T. melanosporum* seedlings, as shown by the close agreement in the native EM fungi appearing in this study and in the one conducted in the same soil with inoculated seedlings (Garcia-Barreda and Reyna 2013). The species-specific effect showed by several treatments on the EM community, together with the various competitive ability of the EM species, adds complexity to the understanding of the long-term effect of each treatment.

The next step to evaluate these soil preparations is to test their effect on the competitiveness of native EM fungi in inoculated plantations in the field. It should also be established if these soil preparations damage the proliferation of the introduced fungi or the seedling development. In the field, seedlings are subject to a more limiting water regime, although the more advanced age and development of inoculated seedlings (1-2 years old) makes them less vulnerable.

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Table S1 – Description of the EM morphotypes.

Morphotype	Colour	Mantle ^a	Emanating elements ^b
<i>Cenococcum geophilum</i>	Black	PL-type G	H: dark brown, thick-walled, non-ramified, non-clamped septa
Type <i>Genea</i>	Reddish brown	PS-type L/K	C: yellowish-reddish, rigid, ramified, enlarged base, non-clamped septa
Type <i>Hebeloma-Cortinarius</i>	Whitish rose to brown	PL-type B	H: hyaline, ramified, enlarged in the septa, clamped, anastomising R: type A, hyaline, with fan-like connection to the mantle
Type <i>Pisolithus</i>	Golden-orange	PL-type B	H: yellowish brown, ramified, sometimes ribbon-like, clamped R: type B, brown, ramified, with inflated cells
Type <i>Russula</i>	Whitish to yellowish brown	PL-type B	C: hyaline, flask-shaped
Type <i>Scleroderma</i>	Pale yellow	PS-type A	H: hyaline-yellowish, ramified, enlarged in the septa, non-clamped septa R: type D, whitish-yellowish, with knot-like structures in ramifications
Type <i>Sebacina</i>	Pale yellow to greyish-brown	PL-PS, type H	H: hyaline, thin, Y-shaped ramification with enlarged walls, scarce and non-clamped septa
Type Thelephoroid	Whitish grey to brown	PL-type D	C: hyaline, awl-shaped, non-ramified, with clamped (when only one) and non-clamped septa H: hyaline, Y-shaped ramification, anastomising, with clamped and non-clamped septa
<i>Tomentella galzinii</i>	Yellowish to greenish brown	PS-type L	C: bristle-like, enlarged base, yellow below the first septa, clamped H: yellow, ramified, clamped R: type A, yellowish-greenish
<i>Trichophaea woolhopeia</i>	Orange to dark brown	PS-type L	C: yellowish, right angle-ramified, non-clamped septa
Type Tuber	Orange to brown	PS-type M	-
Tuber <i>aestivum</i>	Reddish to dark brown	PS-type L	C: reddish, long, non-ramified, zig-zag shaped, non-clamped septa

^a PL: plectenchymatous, PS: pseudoparenchymatous (Agerer, 1987-2002)^b C: cystidia, H: hyphae, R: rhizomorph

Table S1 – Description of the EM morphotypes (continued).

Morphotype	Colour	Mantle ^a	Emanating elements ^b
Complex <i>Tuber albidum</i>	Yellow to brown	PS-type M	C: bristle-like, hyaline to pale yellow, thin, sometimes geniculate base
<i>Tuber melanosporum</i>	Orange to brown	PS-type M	C: yellowish-reddish, right angle-ramified, non-clamped septa
Unidentified 1	Pale yellow to brown	PS-type P	C: hyaline, short, non-ramified, capitate, non-clamped septa H: hyaline-yellow, sometimes with ring-like shapes, ramified, non-clamped septa
Unidentified 3	Reddish brown to black	PS-type O	C: two types, type A and type O, yellow-brown with non-clamped septa H: reddish-brown, ramified, wide, sometimes with warts, with clamped and non-clamped septa
Unidentified 5	Pale yellow to dark brown	PL-type H/I	C: scarce, hyaline, type O, non-clamped septa, sometimes with enlarged cells or covered by crystals H: scarce, hyaline, ramified, non-clamped septa
Unidentified 6	Pale yellow or whitish rose	Type B in young mycorrhizas, type P in the older	H: scarce, hyaline, wide, covered by crystals, Y-shaped ramification, enlarged in or between the septa, sometimes with ring-like shapes, non-clamped septa
Unidentified 7	Reddish black	PS-type O	H: reddish brown, ramified, anastomising, sometimes with warts, with clamped and non-clamped septa R: type C, reddish brown, forming nodia at branching

^a PL: plectenchymatous, PS: pseudoparenchymatous (Agerer, 1987-2002)

^b C: cystidia, H: hyphae, R: rhizomorph

Table S2 – Frequency of appearance of the morphotypes in the quicklime bioassay. Letters indicate significant differences among treatments ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Morphotype	Absolute control	Quicklime (kg m ⁻²)				
		0	0.5	1	1.5	2
<i>C. geophilum</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1
Complex <i>T. albidum</i>	1 a	0.89 a	0.89 a	1 a	0.11 b	1 a
Unidentified 6	0.78 ab	1 a	0.56 b	0.67 ab	0.89 ab	0.33 b
<i>T. galzinii</i>	0.89 a	0 c	0 c	0 c	0.56 ab	0.11 bc
Tipo <i>Sebacina</i>	0.22	0.22	0.11	0	0	0.11
Tipo Teleforoide	0.33	0	0.11	0	0	0
Tipo <i>Scleroderma</i>	0	0	0.11	0	0	0.33
<i>T. aestivum</i>	0	0	0	0.11	0	0.22
Tipo <i>Pisolithus</i>	0.11	0	0	0.11	0	0.11
Tipo <i>Hebeloma/Cortinarius</i>	0	0	0	0.22	0	0
Tipo <i>Genea</i>	0	0	0	0	0.11	0

Table S3 – Percent root colonisation of the three more frequent morphotypes in the quicklime bioassay. Letters indicate significant differences among treatments ($\alpha = 0.05$). The three response variables have been log transformed.

Morphotype	Absolute control	Quicklime (kg m ⁻²)				
		0	0.5	1	1.5	2
<i>C. geophilum</i>	8.0a	6.3ab	10.1a	6.7ab	3.8b	6.2ab
Complex <i>T. albidum</i>	10.8a	4.5a	14.4a	14.0a	0.2b	16.3a
Unidentified 6	1.4b	8.4a	1.0b	0.6b	8.8a	0.1b

Table S4 – Frequency of appearance of the morphotypes in the microwaves-SH-AA bioassay. Letters indicate significant differences among treatment ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Morphotype	Soil preparation						Cultivation time	
	Control	Microw 90 s	Microw 180s	SH 70 g m ⁻²	SH 280 g m ⁻²	AA 315 g m ⁻²	7 months	13 months
Complex <i>T. albidum</i>	1 a	1 a	0.58 b	0.67 b	0.82 ab	1 a	0.83	0.84
Unidentified 6	0.83	1	0.83	0.83	0.64	0.86	0.71 j	0.97 i
<i>C. geophilum</i>	0.83 ab	0.67 b	0 c	0.92 ab	1 a	0.86 ab	0.66	0.74
<i>T. aestivum</i>	1 a	0.25 b	0 b	1 a	1 a	1 a	0.71	0.65
Type <i>Pisolithus</i>	0.08 ab	0 b	0.33 a	0.33 a	0.36 a	0 b	0.23	0.16
Type Theleporoid	0.50 a	0 b	0 b	0.25 ab	0.18 ab	0.14 ab	0.20	0.16
Type <i>Sebacina</i>	0	0	0	0.33	0.18	0	0.06	0.13
Unidentified 1	0.17	0	0	0.08	0.09	0.29	0 j	0.19 i
Unidentified 3	0.17	0	0	0.08	0.09	0	0.11	0
Unidentified 7	0.08	0.25	0	0	0	0	0.06	0.06
<i>T. galzinii</i>	0.08	0	0	0	0	0	0.03	0
Type <i>Tuber</i>	0	0	0	0	0.09	0	0	0.03
Type <i>Hebeloma/</i> <i>Cortinarius</i>	0	0	0	0.08	0	0	0	0.03

Table S5 – Percent root colonisation of the more frequent morphotypes in the microwaves-SH-AA bioassay. Letters indicate significant differences among treatments ($\alpha = 0.05$). The four response variables have been log transformed.

Morphotype	Soil preparation						Cultivation time	
	Control	Microw 90 s	Microw 180s	SH 70 g m ⁻²	SH 280 g m ⁻²	AA 315 g m ⁻²	7 months	13 months
Complex <i>T. albidum</i>	14.4ab	25.3a	4.4bc	2.2c	5.0bc	21.8ab	6.6j	12.0i
Unidentified 6	1.8b	7.6a	4.7ab	1.7b	1.4b	2.8ab	2.7i	3.1i
<i>C. geophilum</i>	2.1a	0.9a	0b	3.2a	2.3a	1.9a	2.6i	1.5i
<i>T. aestivum</i>	18.3a	0.2c	0c	21.8a	26.5a	2.7b	5.5i	4.8i

Table S6 – Frequency of appearance of the morphotypes in the HP-Proxitane-quicklime bioassay. Letters indicate significant differences among treatments ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Morphotype	Soil preparation						Land use		Cultivation time		
	Control	HP 0.6 kg m ⁻²	HP 2.1 kg m ⁻²	Proxitane 2.2 kg m ⁻²	Proxitane 7.7 kg m ⁻²	Quicklime 4 kg m ⁻²	Forest	<i>Qu</i> hedge	6 months	8 months	11 months
Complex <i>T. albidum</i>	0.75	0.73	0.83	0.55	0.45	0.43	0.89 i	0.34 j	0.52	0.70	0.72
Unidentified 6	0.08 ab	0.55 a	0.50 a	0.45 a	0.55 a	0 b	0.37	0.38	0.17 q	0.43 pq	0.56 p
<i>C. geophilum</i>	0.33	0.27	0.17	0.18	0.27	0.14	0.43 i	0 j	0.22 pq	0.09 q	0.44 p
<i>T. woolhopeia</i>	0.17	0.45	0.08	0.18	0.36	0	0.11 j	0.34 i	0.17	0.26	0.22
Type <i>Genea</i>	0.33 a	0.27 ab	0.17 ab	0.09 ab	0 b	0 b	0.11	0.21	0.09 q	0.04 q	0.39 p
Type <i>Pisolithus</i>	0.08	0.27	0.08	0.09	0.09	0	0.06	0.17	0.09	0.17	0.06
Type <i>Tuber</i>	0	0.18	0.17	0	0.18	0	0.11	0.07	0.09	0.04	0.17
Type <i>Russula</i>	0.08	0.18	0	0	0	0	0.06	0.03	0.13	0	0
<i>T. aestivum</i>	0	0.18	0.08	0	0	0	0.09	0	0	0	0.17
Type Thelephoroid	0.08	0	0.08	0	0	0	0.06	0	0.09	0	0
Unidentified 3	0	0.18	0	0	0	0	0.06	0	0	0	0.11
Unidentified 5	0.08	0.09	0	0	0	0	0.06	0	0	0.09	0
<i>T. melanosporum</i>	0	0	0.08	0	0	0	0	0.03	0	0.04	0
Unidentified 1	0	0.09	0	0	0	0	0.03	0	0.04	0	0

Table S7 – Percent root colonisation of the more frequent morphotype in the HP-Proxitane-quicklime bioassay. Letters indicate significant differences among treatments ($\alpha = 0.05$). The response variables has been log transformed.

Complex <i>T. albidum</i> (%)	
Soil preparation	
Control	4.0 a
HP 0.6 kg m ⁻²	1.6 ab
HP 2.1 kg m ⁻²	3.7 a
Proxitane 2.2 kg m ⁻²	1.0 ab
Proxitane 7.7 kg m ⁻²	0.7 ab
Quicklime 4 kg m ⁻²	0.3 b
Land use	
Forest	9.3 a
<i>Q. ilex</i> hedgerow in cereal culture	0.1 b
Cultivation time	
6 months	1.0
8 months	1.7
11 months	1.5